

SYNTHESIS OF SOME NEW ACRIDINE DERIVATIVES. PART I

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Certain dialkylamino-alkylamino-acridines, substituted phenylamino-acridines, sulphanilamido-acridines and acetylaminobenzene sulphonamido-acridines have been synthesised for studying their antimalarial and antiseptic properties.

Acridine derivatives, like atebirin and acriquine, which contain a dialkylamino-alkylamino chain at position 5, possess strong antimalarial properties (Kikuth, *Deut. Med. Wchschr.*, 1932, **58**, 530; Magidson and Grigorowsky, *Ber.*, 1936, **69B**, 396; Mietsch and Mauss, *Klin. Wchschr.*, 1933, **12**, 1276; Magidson and Grigorowsky, *Khim. Farm. Prom.*, 1935, No 1, 26-34). Magidson and Grigorowsky (*loc. cit.*) have noticed that the antimalarial chemotherapeutic index of 8-nitro derivatives is increased if the nitro group is transferred from 8 to 7 position in the acridine molecule. Further, the acridines, which are substituted by a halogen atom in any particular position, show antimalarial properties (Mietsch and Mauss, *loc. cit.*).

5-Aminoacridines, which contain a nitro or amino group, have been shown to possess good antiseptic properties (Schnitzar and Silberstein, *Z. Hyg. Infek.*, 1929, **109**, 519; Albert *et al.*, *Brit. J. Exptl. Path.*, 1938, **19**, 41).

In view of the above facts it was thought desirable to prepare compounds of the general formula

where-NHR represents different straight chained dialkylamino-alkylamino, substituted phenylamino, sulphanilamide, amino, and *p*-acetylaminobenzene sulphonylamino groups. The nitro group was further reduced to amino group and the latter acetylated and also condensed with *p*-acetylaminobenzene sulphonyl chloride.

To obtain these compounds 5-nitro-*N-p*-chlorophenylanthranilic acid was cyclised with phosphorus oxychloride to give 7-nitro-3:5-dichloroacridine. 7-Nitro-3:5-dichloroacridine has further been condensed with aniline, *p*-anisidine, *p*-chloroaniline, *p*-aminobenzene sulphonamide, γ -diethylaminopropylamine and δ -diethylaminobutylamine according to Method I.

In the condensation of ϵ -diethylaminoamylamine with the dichloroacridine by Method I, much of acridone was formed, consequently the condensation was accomplished according to Method II.

7-Nitro-3-chloro-5-aminoacridine was obtained by the treatment of 7-nitro-3:5-dichloroacridine with ammonium carbonate in hot phenolic solution. This 5-aminoacridine was further condensed with *p*-acetylaminobenzene sulphonyl chloride in dry pyridine.

7-Nitro-3-chloro-5(phenyl) aminoacridine and 7-nitro-3-chloro-5(4'-methoxyphenyl)-aminoacridine were further reduced by anhydrous stannous chloride, acetic anhydride and hydrochloric acid. These reduced 7-amino groups were further acetylated and also were condensed with *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphonyl chloride in dry pyridine to yield the corresponding 7-*p'*-acetaminobenzene sulphonylamino-3-chloro-5-substituted acridines.

EXPERIMENTAL

7-Nitro-3:5-dichloroacridine.—5-Nitro-*N-p*-chlorophenylanthranilic acid (1 g.) was refluxed with excess of phosphorus oxychloride (6 c.c.) for 4 hours on an oil-bath. The oxychloride was removed by distillation under reduced pressure. The residue was triturated with cold ammonia, filtered, washed, and dried in a steam-oven. On crystallisation from dry benzene, it gave yellow needles, m. p. 208-209°. (Found: N, 9.71. $C_{13}H_8O_2N_2Cl_2$ requires N, 9.66 per cent).

7-Nitro-3-chloroacridone.—The insoluble portion, which was left on crystallisation of 7-nitro-3:5-dichloroacridine from benzene, on washing with hot alcohol, chloroform, acetone and ether gave a product which did not melt up to 400°. This could not be crystallised from any of the organic solvents. On analysis it gave N, 10.46%, while the acridone $C_{13}H_7O_2N_2Cl$ requires N, 10.20%. So the result of analysis shows that it is 7-nitro-2-chloroacridone.

4-Nitro-4'-chlorodiphenylamine-6-carboxyl Chloride.—5-Nitro-*N-p*-chlorophenylanthranilic acid (1 g.) was suspended in 8 c.c. of dry benzene and phosphorus pentachloride (0.9 g.) was added to it. It was refluxed for 15 minutes until a solution was obtained. On filtration and cooling, it deposited yellow powder which was crystallised from dry benzene, m. p. 135-36°, yield 80%. (Found: N, 9.27. $C_{13}H_8O_3N_2Cl_2$ requires N, 9.0 per cent).

7-Nitro-3-chloro-5-aminoacridine.—7-Nitro-3:5-dichloroacridine (1 g.) was heated with phenol (5 g.) up to 70°. Then ammonium carbonate (1 g) was added slowly and temperature raised to 120° for 15 minutes. The reaction mixture was treated with ether, and dry hydrochloric acid gas passed through it. The hydrochloride after washing with acetone, was treated with sodium hydroxide solution and the base was crystallised from chloroform, m. p. 303-304°. (Found: N, 15.66. $C_{13}H_8O_2N_2Cl_2$ requires N, 15.35 per cent).

7-Nitro-3-chloro-5-(*p'*-acetylamino benzene sulphonyl) aminoacridine.—The solution of 7-nitro-2-chloro-9-aminoacridine (1 g.) in dry pyridine (20 c.c.) was heated to 125° for 3 hours with *p*-acetylamino benzene sulphonyl chloride (1.4 g.). Yellow needles were deposited on cooling. It was filtered and crystallised from dry pyridine as bright yellow needles, m. p. 356-58°. (Found: N, 12.18. $C_{21}H_{15}O_6N_2ClS$ requires N, 11.90 per cent).

7-Nitro-3-chloro-5-substituted Acridines (Method I).—7-Nitro-3:5-dichloroacridine (1 g., 1 mol.) was dissolved in phenol (5 g.) and the amine (1.1 mol.) to be condensed was added. The mixture was heated on a steam-bath for 3 hours. After cooling, the reaction mixture was thoroughly triturated with ether. The product was filtered

and thoroughly washed with ether. It was usually crystallised from glacial acetic acid. The free base was obtained by treatment with sodium hydroxide solution.

7-Nitro-3-chloro-5-(phenyl) aminoacridine.—The hydrochloride was crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m. p. 320-21°. (Found: N, 11.03. $C_{19}H_{13}O_2N_3Cl \cdot HCl$ requires N, 10.88 per cent). The base was crystallised from 80% alcohol as orange needles, m. p. 255-56°.

7-Nitro-3-chloro-5-(4'-methoxyphenyl) aminoacridine.—The hydrochloride was crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m. p. 307-309° (decomp.). (Found: N, 10.30. $C_{20}H_{11}O_3N_3Cl \cdot HCl$ requires N, 10.09 per cent). The base was crystallised from benzene, m. p. 239-40°.

7-Nitro-3-chloro-5-(4'-chlorophenyl) aminoacridine.—The hydrochloride was crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m. p. 332-34° (decomp.). (Found: N, 10.08. $C_{19}H_{11}O_2N_3Cl_2 \cdot HCl$ requires N, 9.99 per cent). The base on crystallisation from 80% alcohol yielded beautiful scarlet needles, m. p. 266-67°.

7-Nitro-3-chloro-5-(4'-sulphonamidophenyl) aminoacridine was crystallised from acetone, m. p. 282-83°. (Found: N, 13.23. $C_{19}H_{13}O_4N_4ClS$ requires N, 13.07 per cent).

7-Nitro-3-chloro-5-(γ -diethylaminopropyl) aminoacridine.—The condensation was effected as given in Method I, with some difference in working out the product. After trituration with ether the semi-solid obtained was treated with 2-N-sodium hydroxide solution and the free base was washed with alkali and then with water. It was separated from any acridone by treating with dilute hydrochloric acid in which the acridone was insoluble. Then the hydrochloride solution was washed with ether, the ether separated, and the remaining hydrochloride solution was filtered and again neutralised with 2N-sodium hydroxide. The free base was separated, dissolved in ether and dried over fused magnesium sulphate. The dry ethereal solution was treated with a few drops of absolute alcohol, saturated with hydrochloric acid gas. A yellow powder of dihydrochloride separated. It was thoroughly triturated with ether and crystallised from a mixture of equal quantities of alcohol and acetone as bright yellow micro-crystals, m. p. 212-14°. (Found: N, 12.36. $C_{20}H_{23}O_2N_4Cl \cdot 2HCl$ requires N, 12.10 per cent).

7-Nitro-3-chloro-5-(δ -diethylaminobutyl) aminoacridine was worked out as above, and crystallised from absolute alcohol as yellow glistening needles, m. p. 224-26°. (Found: N, 12.12. $C_{21}H_{25}O_2N_4Cl \cdot 2HCl$ requires N, 11.82 per cent).

7-Nitro-3-chloro-5-(ϵ -diethylaminoamyl) aminoacridine (Method II).—In this condensation by the above method, a lot of acridone was formed. 4-Nitro-4'-chlorodiphenylamine-6-carboxyl chloride (1 g.) was taken up in 10 c.c. of dry benzene, and then ϵ -diethylaminoamylamine (0.7 g.) was added to it. The mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 30 minutes. After this 3 c.c. of phosphorus oxychloride were added to it and refluxing continued for 6 hours. After cooling, benzene was decanted off and the residue washed thoroughly with ether. It was then taken up in 15 c.c. of hot absolute alcohol and 50 c.c. of ether were added to it. A yellow powder separated out, which was crystallised from a mixture of absolute alcohol and acetone, m. p. 235-36°. (Found: N, 11.57. $C_{22}H_{27}O_2N_4Cl \cdot HCl$ requires N, 11.40 per cent).

7-Amino-3-chloro-5-(phenyl)aminoacridine.—The reducing agent was prepared by suspending anhydrous stannous chloride (7 g.) in acetic anhydride (7 c.c.) and then adding glacial acetic acid to make the volume up to 30 c.c. and then saturating with dry hydrochloric acid gas till the whole of stannous chloride went into solution.

7-Nitro-3-chloro-5-(phenyl)aminoacridine (1 g.) was added in small portions to 30 c.c. of the reducing agent with continuous stirring, the whole operation lasting for one hour. It was then left overnight, filtered and washed with glacial acetic acid. The free base was obtained by treating with potassium hydroxide solution. It was then washed free of alkali. After drying it was crystallised from a mixture of absolute alcohol and chloroform in bright yellow needles, m. p. 236-37°, yield 90%. (Found: N, 13.39. $C_{19}H_{14}N_3Cl$ requires N, 13.15 per cent).

7-Amino-3-chloro-5-(4'-methoxyphenyl)aminoacridine was obtained by the reduction of 7-nitro-3-chloro-5-(4'-methoxyphenyl) aminoacridine by the above method and crystallised from a mixture of absolute alcohol and chloroform in yellow glistening plates, m. p. 220-21°. (Found: N, 12.44. $C_{20}H_{16}ON_3Cl$ requires N, 12.01 per cent).

7-Acetylamino-3-chloro-5-(phenyl) aminoacridine.—7-Amino-3-chloro-5-(phenyl)-aminoacridine (0.1 g.) was heated with a mixture of acetic anhydride and glacial acetic acid (30 c.c.) on a water-bath for 15 minutes. It was then poured into ice-cold water, made alkaline with ammonia solution, filtered, washed, dried and crystallised from absolute alcohol, m. p. 286-87°. (Found: N, 11.83. $C_{21}H_{16}ON_3Cl$ requires N, 11.61 per cent).

7-Acetylamino-3-chloro-5-(4'-methoxyphenyl)aminoacridine.—Acetylation was made as in the above case. It was crystallised from absolute alcohol as shining scarlet needles, m. p. 258-59°. (Found: N, 10.94. $C_{22}H_{18}O_2N_3Cl$ requires N, 10.72 per cent).

7-p'-Acetaminobenzene-sulphonylamino-3-chloro-5-(phenyl) aminoacridine.—7-Amino-3-chloro-5-(phenyl)aminoacridine (0.2 g.) was dissolved in freshly distilled dry pyridine (8 c.c.). Then *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphonyl chloride (0.24 g.) was added to the pyridine solution and left overnight and then heated in a paraffin-bath at 125° for 2 hours. After cooling, it was triturated with 30 c.c. of water and filtered and washed thoroughly with water. It could not be crystallised from various organic solvents. For analysis it was washed thoroughly with boiling absolute alcohol, chloroform, and ether. It is an orange powder, m. p. 282-83°. (Found: N, 10.99. $C_{27}H_{21}O_3N_4ClS$ requires N, 10.84 per cent).

7-p'-Acetaminobenzene-sulphonylamino-3-chloro-5-(4'-methoxyphenyl) aminoacridine.—It was prepared by the same procedure as the above compound, and crystallised as an orange powder, m. p. 256-57°. (Found: N, 10.46. $C_{28}H_{23}O_4N_4ClS$ requires N 10.24 per cent).

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